

**DETERMINATION OF TEMPERATURE RISE OF ACTIVE PARTS OF THE
REVITALIZED GENERATOR FROM HEAT RUN TEST**

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ABSTRACT

In order to ensure safety and reliability of the energy production, it is necessary to provide stable operation of synchronous generators since they represent basic energy production units. Hydrogenerators are subjected to a wide variety of operating conditions but however, they are designed to achieve a lifespan of more than 35 years. Heating of generator parts is caused by power losses: Joule losses in the armature winding, stator core losses, Joule losses in the field winding, ventilation and friction losses, additional losses etc. The generator cooling system is in charge of heat removal from the generator. Air-cooling is one of the three possible methods of generator cooling and it is a standard cooling concept for hydrogenerators. Overheating of parts of the generator can be detrimental and can lead to unplanned outages. Furthermore, the consequences of overheating can be very serious and might cause expensive refurbishments. Having this in mind, it is of great importance to make an accurate model of generator heat transfer and to provide adequate cooling of the generator. A temperature rise of a part of the generator must be lower than the corresponding predetermined value for all operating conditions if designed lifespan is to be reached.

The purpose of the heat run test is to determine the maximum values of temperatures and temperature rises of active parts of the generator while it is operating with rated load and rated power factor. During the heat run test, the generator operates at different regimes, starting from the smallest load and increasing the load up to the rated load. After reaching the thermal steady state, measurements are performed. Based on the results of measurements in each of the generator operating regimes, the maximum values of temperatures and temperature rises of active parts of the generator are obtained. Sometimes it is not possible to perform certain operating regimes at the plant (for example the rated load), but using results from performed tests it is possible to estimate the maximum values of temperatures and temperature rises of parts of the generator in that regime.

The maximum values of temperatures and temperature rises of parts of the generator in certain operating regime can be determined using a polynomial fitting. On the other side, when it is necessary to determine the maximum values of temperature rises of parts of the generator due to voltage and frequency deviations from its rated values, the procedure described in this paper can be applied.

KEYWORDS

Hydrogenerator, heat run test, the temperature rise of the stator winding and the stator core, the temperature rise of the field winding, voltage deviation, frequency deviation

INTRODUCTION

The significance of synchronous generators as basic energy production units is indisputable. In case of some failure of synchronous generator, in addition to repair costs, significantly higher problem are the economic losses caused by undelivered electric energy. Also, overheating of certain parts of the synchronous generator might be one of the potential problems during the exploitation of the generator.

A P-Q diagram of synchronous generator defines boundaries within which generator can operate safely. The limits of continuous operation are determined by rated values of power and current, as well as the limitations related to the stability, ratings of the prime mover, generator parts overheating etc. Stator and rotor heating of the synchronous generator represents one of the limiting factors during exploitation of the synchronous generator. For this reason it is very important to determine the temperature rise of certain parts of the synchronous generator above a reference temperature during operation under a specified loading condition and to establish if it is lower than permissible.

In electrical machines, the problem of heat distribution is equally important as different other factors due to the fact that the increase of temperature inside the machine directly affects the maximum continuously operating power of the machine. When constructing a new machine, empirical knowledge can be useful but on the other hand it is necessary to model and analyze the heat transfer problem in detail. The accuracy of the model and calculation is checked during machine testing.

The relationship between the insulation lifetime and temperature during operation of the machine represents one of the most important factors in the construction and operation of the electrical machine. During exploitation, the insulation material is affected by thermal aging. Therefore, mechanical and dielectric strength is deteriorated. The maximum temperature rise for each class of insulation is determined in the standards [1] and should not be exceeded.

POWER LOSSES, HEATING AND COOLING METHODS

A temperature rise of certain parts of the synchronous generator represents the difference between the temperature of that part measured by the appropriate method and the temperature of the coolant (reference temperature). Temperature rise can be determined during the heat run test of synchronous generator which can be performed by one of four available methods. According to Conventional loading method synchronous generator should operate with the specified load that is determined by armature current, power, voltage and frequency until the machine reaches thermal equilibrium [2]. Readings of temperatures should be taken every half hour or less. Thermal equilibrium (steady state) is reached when the temperature of a part of the machine is less or equal than 1K within 1 hour. Conventional loading test should be performed at several loadings of the generator (for example $P=0.5P_n$; $P=0.75P_n$ and $P=P_n$) and at the same time maintaining the generator voltage at rated value [3]. However, it is difficult to meet all these requirements in practice; because of the high voltage in the grid or small net head, for example. A temperature rise of a part of the synchronous generator is determined for each measured regime. Generator manufacturers define the permissible temperature rise for parts of a synchronous generator for the rated load. But since it is not always possible to perform heat run tests at all desired regimes, temperature rise is then calculated for the rated load.

Heat run test was performed during performance testing of revitalized hydrogenerator at one of the power plants which is part of the Serbian power grid. Basic technical data of revitalized generator are presented in table 1. Picture from the site is presented in Fig. 1.

Table 1- Basic technical data of revitalized generator

Rated apparent power	37000 kVA
Rated power factor	0.85
Rated stator voltage	11000 V
Rated stator current	1942 A
Rated speed	136.36 min ⁻¹
Rated frequency	50 Hz
Rated field voltage	196 V
Rated field current	759 A
Number of phases	3
Connection	Y
Insulation class	F

Fig. 1: Hydrogenerator at the site

Power losses within hydrogenerator represent sources of heat which increases the temperature of all parts of the generator and which have to be conducted away. There are three possible cooling methods for hydrogenerators: air-cooling, water-cooling and evaporation-cooling [4]. The most common is the air-cooling concept because of its simplicity, maintenance and reliability. In this way, air is used to take the heat from the parts of generator and then transfer it to water in generator coolers. Cold cooling air flow is divided into two parts. The first part flows between rotor poles in the axial direction and removes heat from rotor poles and the second flows radially and passes through stator ventilation ducts removing heat from stator winding and stator core. Hot air is then directed to the generator water coolers placed on the stator frame, where water takes over heat from the air. After passing through generator water coolers, cold cooling air is again divided into two parts and starts a new cycle of cooling.

HEAT RUN TEST OF THE REVITALIZED GENERATOR

Heat run test of revitalized hydrogenerator was performed during performance tests in order to determine temperature rises of parts of the generator while the generator was connected to the grid. During this test generator was at different loads (regimes of operation that are presented in table 2) and for each of them temperature rise of parts of the generator was determined. Following electrical values were measured: three phase stator voltages, three phase stator currents, generator active and reactive power, frequency, field voltage and field current; and following temperatures: stator winding and stator core, field winding, cold and hot cooling air, cold and hot cooling water, upper guide bearing, lower guide bearing and thrust bearing. Measurements were taken every half hour until thermal equilibrium was established.

Table 2 – Regimes of operation during heat run test

Regime I	P=19MW; cosφ _r =0.85	Regime III	P=29MW (P _{max} *); cosφ _r =0.85
Regime II	P=29MW; Q=25MVar; I≈I _r	Regime IV	P=22MW; Q=-10MVar

P_{max}* refers to maximum active power which could be reached during particular heat run test

Measured temperatures during heat run test and field current are presented in table 3 in which temperature of field winding refers to recalculated value, using ohmic resistance of field winding during heat run test and ohmic resistance at 20°C. All presented values in this table correspond to final values measured at thermal steady state condition. Labels used in this table are:

θ_{sw}, θ_{sc}, θ_{fw} – the temperature of the stator winding, the stator core and a field winding, respectively

θ_{ca}, θ_{wa}, θ_{cw}, θ_{ww} – the temperature of cold/warm air and water, respectively

$\theta_{ug}, \theta_{lg}, \theta_t$ – the temperature of the upper guide, lower guide and thrust bearing

I_f – field (rotor) current

Table 3 - Measured temperatures during heat run test and field current

	Stator		Rotor	Cooling air		Cooling water		Bearings			Field current
	θ_{sw}	θ_{sc}	θ_{fw}	θ_{ca}	θ_{wa}	θ_{cw}	θ_{ww}	θ_{ug}	θ_{lg}	θ_t	I_f [A]
Regime I	64,8	61,7	71,0	40,8	54,6	7,1	44,3	50,1	53,7	41,3	593,7
Regime II	89,4	76,6	105,4	40,6	66,5	7,2	44,0	50,7	54,1	40,4	839,7
Regime III	78,6	68,6	85,1	38,7	59,8	7,4	41,3	50,1	54,2	40,6	722,7
Regime IV	63,4	57,9	51,1	38,6	51,9	7,3	41,4	49,6	53,6	41,5	345,7

Field winding temperatures θ_f and temperature rise $\Delta\theta_f$ are presented in table 4. Field winding temperature rise $\Delta\theta_f$ against field current squared is presented in Fig. 2. Field winding temperature rise at rated field current is determined from the graph and it equals 49,3 K and is well below the permissible temperature limit for this class of insulation (F class).

Table 4 – Field (rotor) winding temperature and field winding temperature rise

No. Regime	U_f	I_f	R_f	θ_f	θ_{ca}	$\Delta\theta_f$	P_f
	[V]	[A]	[Ω]	[$^{\circ}\text{C}$]		[K]	[kW]
I	144,90	594,00	0,24394	71,3	40,7	30,7	86,07
II	227,57	839,83	0,27097	105,2	40,5	64,7	191,12
III	183,64	721,25	0,25461	84,7	38,7	46,0	132,45
IV	78,97	345,33	0,22868	52,1	38,7	13,4	27,27

U_f, I_f, R_f, P_f - the field winding voltage, current, ohmic resistance and Joule losses, respectively

Fig. 2: Field winding temperature rise vs field current squared

Stator winding temperature rise $\Delta\theta_{sw}$ against stator current squared is presented in Fig. 3. Stator winding temperature rise at rated stator current is determined from the graph and it equals 46,4 K and is well below the permissible temperature limit for this class of insulation (F class).

Stator core temperature rise $\Delta\theta_{sc}$ against armature current squared is presented in Fig. 4. Stator core temperature rise at rated armature current is determined from the graph and it equals 33,5 K and is well below the permissible temperature limit for designed stator core.

Fig. 3: Stator winding temperature rise vs armature current squared

Fig. 4: Stator core temperature rise vs armature current squared

Temperatures θ_{sw} , θ_{sc} and temperature rises $\Delta\theta_{sw}$, $\Delta\theta_{sc}$ of the stator winding and core are presented in tables 5 and 6.

Table 5 – Stator winding temperature and temperature rise

No. Regime	θ_{sw}	θ_{ca}	$\Delta\theta_{sw}$ [K]
	[°C]		
I	64,8	40,7	24,1
II	89,4	40,5	48,9
III	78,3	38,7	39,6
IV	63,5	38,7	24,8

Table 6 - Stator core temperature and temperature rise

No. Regime	θ_{sc}	θ_{ca}	$\Delta\theta_{sc}$ [K]
	[°C]		
I	61,7	40,7	21,0
II	76,6	40,5	36,1
III	68,4	38,7	29,7
IV	58,0	38,7	19,3

In addition to preinstalled temperature sensors that were used for temperature measurements, thermal tapes were stuck on stator winding just before the beginning of the first regime of the heat run test. After finishing 4th regime of the heat run test, thermal tapes were removed and it was established that the temperature did not exceed 104°C (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Thermal tapes on stator winding before heat run test (left) and after finishing the test (right)

RECALCULATION OF TEMPERATURE RISE DUE TO VOLTAGE AND FREQUENCY DEVIATIONS

The temperature rise of the stator winding and stator core can be corrected to the rated load point using the following formula:

$$\Delta\theta_{sw,sc} = \Delta\theta_E * \left(\frac{E_r}{E}\right)^2 + \Delta\theta_I * \left(\frac{I_r}{I}\right)^2 + \Delta\theta_0 \tag{1}$$

Following symbols are used in the formula:

$\Delta\theta_E, \Delta\theta_I, \Delta\theta_0$ – temperature rise due to voltage-dependent losses, current-dependent losses and ventilation losses, respectively

E, I, E_r, I_r – Air gap voltage and stator current at test load point and at rated load point, respectively

X_L – calculated leakage reactance for stator winding = 0,174 p.u.

Air-gap voltage is calculated as $E = \sqrt{U^2 + I^2 * X_L^2 + 2 * I * X_L * U * \sin\varphi}$. At the end of the 2nd regime of the heat run test: $U=11318,9$ V= 1,029 p.u.; $I=1943$ A= 1,0005 p.u. and $E=1,151$ p.u.

The temperature rises $\Delta\theta_E$ and $\Delta\theta_I$ are presented in table 8 and are determined from idle running (*,_{IR}), no-load (*,_{IRE}) and the 2nd regime of the heat run test (*,2) according to table 7.

Table 7 – Calculated values and temperatures. Temperatures that are measured in stationary temperature states. Temperatures at the idle run operating mode, with and without excitation, were measured during execution of calorimetric tests for generator efficiency determination.

	U[V]	U[p.u.]	I[A]	I[p.u.]	E[p.u.]	θ_{sc} [°C]	θ_{sw} [°C]	θ_{ca} [°C]
Idle run (*, _{IR})	0	0	0	0	0	16,9	16,7	14,9
No-load (*, _{IRE})	10979	0,998	0	0	0,998	34,1	31,3	20,3
Heat run II (*,2)	11319	1,029	1943	1,000	1,151	76,6	89,4	40,6
Rated point	11000	1,000	1942	1,000	1,102	- / -	- / -	- / -
Guarantee point	11000	1,000	1942	1,000	1,102	- / -	- / -	40,0

Table 8 – Temperature rise due to voltage and current dependent losses

	$\Delta\theta_E$ [°C]	$\Delta\theta_I$ [°C]	$\Delta\theta_0$ [°C]
Stator winding	$(\theta_{sw,IRE}-\theta_{ca,IRE})-(\theta_{sw,IR}-\theta_{ca,IR})=9,2$	$(\theta_{sw,2}-\theta_{ca,2})-(\theta_{sw,IR}-\theta_{ca,IR})-\Delta\theta_E \cdot (E_2/E_{IR})^2=34,8$	1,8
Stator core	$(\theta_{sc,IRE}-\theta_{ca,IRE})-(\theta_{sc,IR}-\theta_{ca,IR})=11,8$	$(\theta_{sc,2}-\theta_{ca,2})-(\theta_{sc,IR}-\theta_{ca,IR})-\Delta\theta_E \cdot (E_2/E_{IR})^2=18,3$	2,0

Now, stator winding and stator core temperature rises are calculated using formula (1):

$$\Delta\theta_{Cu} = \Delta\theta_E * \left(\frac{E_n}{E_{IRE}}\right)^2 + \Delta\theta_I * \left(\frac{I_n}{I_2}\right)^2 + \Delta\theta_0 = 9,2 * \left(\frac{1.102}{0,998}\right)^2 + 34,8 * \left(\frac{1.000}{1.0005}\right)^2 + 1,8 = 47,8 K$$

$$\Delta\theta_{Fe} = \Delta\theta_E * \left(\frac{E_n}{E_{IRE}}\right)^2 + \Delta\theta_I * \left(\frac{I_n}{I_2}\right)^2 + \Delta\theta_0 = 11,8 * \left(\frac{1.102}{0,998}\right)^2 + 18,3 * \left(\frac{1.000}{1.0005}\right)^2 + 2,0 = 34,7 K$$

The temperature rise for the field winding can be corrected to guarantee load point using the following formula [3] (when $\Delta\theta_{fan}=0$):

$$\Delta\theta_f = \left(\frac{i_f}{i_{f,2}}\right)^2 * \Delta\theta_{f,2} * \frac{235 + \theta_{air,ref}}{235 + \Delta\theta_{f,2} + \theta_{air,2} - \left(\frac{i_f}{i_{f,2}}\right)^2 * \Delta\theta_{f,2}} = 48,6 K$$

where:

$i_f = 746,1 A$; rated field current (determined from the measured regulation curve at rated power factor)

$i_{f,2} = 839,8 A$; the field current at the end of the 2nd regime of the heat run test

$\theta_{f,2} = 105,4^\circ C$, the field winding temperature at the end of the 2nd regime of the heat run test

$\Delta\theta_{f,2} = 64,8^\circ C$, the field winding temperature rise at the end of the 2nd regime of the heat run test

$\theta_{air,ref} = 40,0^\circ C$, the cold cooling air reference temperature

$\theta_{air,2} = 40,6^\circ C$, the cold cooling air temperature at the end of the 2nd regime of the heat run test

Calculated values for the temperature rises of the stator winding and stator core, as well as field winding are in good accordance with measured temperature rises during performance of the heat run test and obtained temperature rises from Fig. 2-4 (conventional loading).

Temperature rise evaluation considering voltage variations $\Delta U = \pm 10\% U_r$ and $\pm 7,5\% U_r$

Voltage drop on Potier reactance is:

$$U_{xp} = I \cdot X_p = \sqrt{E_p^2 - (U \cdot \cos \varphi)^2} - U \cdot \sin \varphi$$

Where e.m.f E_p is calculated using following formula:

$$E_p = \sqrt{(U \cdot \cos \varphi)^2 + (I \cdot X_p + U \cdot \sin \varphi)^2}$$

for $\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 7,5\%$ voltage deviation from the rated voltage, while, also, each corresponding current deviation is calculated at the rated load. Then, from the measured no-load characteristic, for every E_p corresponding Δi_f is obtained in order to calculate the rotor winding temperature rise (i_{fg} and i_{fk} are excitation current corresponding to the rated voltage and rated current on the no-load saturation curve and on the short-circuit curve, respectively) [5]:

$$i_f = \Delta i_f + \sqrt{(i_{fg} + i_{fk} \cdot \sin \varphi)^2 + (i_{fk} \cdot \cos \varphi)^2}$$

In the same way, air gap voltage E is calculated for each value of voltage deviation, and depending on it, each corresponding current deviation is calculated from the rated value. Also, corrections of the voltage and current dependent losses were done based on the corresponding voltage and current deviations. All calculations are done based on the assumption that generator operates with the rated power factor and rated apparent power. Temperature rises for stator winding, stator core and field winding at rated load are presented in Table 9, based on the corresponding voltage deviations.

Table 9 - Temperature rises for stator winding, stator core and field winding at rated load considering voltage deviations

ΔU [% U_r]	-10%	+10%	-7,5%	+7,5%
$\Delta\theta_{sw}$ [°C]	52,6	41,3	50,6	42,2
$\Delta\theta_{sc}$ [°C]	34,6	30,9	33,8	31,1
$\Delta\theta_f$ [°C]	42,1	60,7	42,9	56,0

Temperature rise evaluation considering frequency variations $\Delta f = -2/+3\%$

The following formulas are used to extrapolate temperature rises for frequency variations:

$$\Delta\theta_{air} = \frac{\Delta\theta_{air,test}}{f}$$

$$\Delta\theta_f = \Delta\theta_{f,test} * \left(\frac{1}{f}\right)^2 + (\Delta\theta_{air} - \Delta\theta_{air,test})$$

$$\Delta\theta_{sw} = \Delta\theta_{sw,test} + (\Delta\theta_{air} - \Delta\theta_{air,test})$$

$$\Delta\theta_{sc} = \Delta\theta_{sc,test} + (\Delta\theta_{air} - \Delta\theta_{air,test})$$

The stator core, stator winding and field winding temperature rises as function of frequency and voltage deviation are presented in Table 10.

Table 10 - Temperature rise of stator winding, stator core and field winding at rated load considering voltage deviation and frequency deviation

Δf [% f_r]	-2%		+3%		-2%		+3%	
ΔU [% U_r]	-10%	+10%	-10%	+10%	-7,5%	+7,5%	-7,5%	+7,5%
$\Delta\theta_{sw}$ [°C]	53,1	41,8	51,8	40,5	51,1	42,7	50,1	41,7
$\Delta\theta_{sc}$ [°C]	35,1	31,4	33,8	30,1	34,3	31,6	33,3	30,6
$\Delta\theta_f$ [°C]	44,4	63,7	38,9	56,5	45,2	58,8	40,7	53,3

SUMMARY

In this paper method for determination of temperature rise of the stator winding and the stator core, as well as rotor winding, during operation of hydrogenerator is presented. Problematic of power losses as a source of heating and heat distribution inside the generator are described. The heat run test of revitalized hydrogenerator that is performed at the power plant is described in detail and measured data during heat run test are presented. Furthermore, method for calculation of temperature rise of parts of hydrogenerator at rated load, based on measured data, is shown. In addition to this, method for calculation of temperature rises of stator winding and stator core and field winding due to voltage and frequency variations is presented. Comparison between measured values and values obtained from the calculations show good accuracy of the presented methods.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

[1] IEC, „International Standard, Rotating electrical machines, Part 1: Rating and performance“, IEC Standard 60034-1, Edition 12.0, 2010-02

[2] Ion Boldea, The Electric Generators Handbook, Synchronous generators, CRC Press, Taylor&Francis Group, 2006.

[3] IEEE Guide: Test Procedures for Synchronous machines, Part I Acceptance and Performance Testing, Part II Test procedures and parameter Determination for Dynamic Analysis, IEEE Std 115-1995 (R2002)

[4] Greg C. Stone, Edward A. Boulter, Ian Culbert, Hussein Dhirani, „Electrical Insulation for rotating machines, Design, Evaluation, Aging, Testing, and Repair“, IEEE PRESS, 2004.

[5] IEC, „International Standard, Rotating electrical machines, Part 4: Methods for determining synchronous machine quantities from tests“, IEC Standard 60034-4, Edition 3.0, 2008-05